

ISic3674

Fragment of a Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

Unknown (honorific or dedication?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2017-07-24

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

From material found in trenches L, LI and LX excavated by Carettoni in 1956, along the front of and within the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997959, 14.262601

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

Fragment of a white marble plaque, broken top, left and below, but seemingly preserving part of the right margin. The rear is very rough and unfinished

Dimensions

Height 14.4 cm

Width 17.3 cm

Depth not measured cm

Layout

Parts of two lines of Latin letters are preserved set between guidelines top and bottom.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Regular v-cut letters with small serifs: E has equal length bars; M has all bars off vertical and the mid-point reaches down to the line; R is closed, with the tail extending off the eye; interpunct formed in the style of a comma

Letter heights:

Line 2: 50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 30 mm

Text

undefined. []

1. [---]ram[]

2. [---]evir ·

undefined. []

Apparatus

Text from autopsy and photographs

Carettoni: [---]RM

Carettoni: [--]FVIR[-]; Facella: [S]EVIR

Translation

Commentary

In line 1, the space and form of the second letter is too great to be an R (compare line 2), and must be an A; the preceding stroke is compatible with the tail of an R. As Facella 2006: 289 n.35 already observed, FVIR is implausible and the only other letter restorable from the traces is an E, which is in turn entirely plausible for the reading 'Sevir'. Given that the word appears in the nominative, a dedication by a *sevir*, of which there are several examples already from Halaesa (e.g. ISic0804 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0804>] and ISic3576 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3576>]), therefore seems more likely than an honorific text. The distinctive comma-like interpunct is attested in other Halaesian inscriptions, such as ISic3572 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3572>] , ISic3573 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3573>] , and ISic3589 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3589>] .

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Bibliography

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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 295 no.12c
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